

Synthesis of *O,O'*-alkylenedithiophosphato complexes of cobalt

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Manuscript received 6 October 1998, accepted 11 March 1999

Complexes of the type $[\text{Co}\{\text{S}_2\text{PO}_2\text{G}\}_2]$ ($\text{G} = -\text{CMe}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CHMe}-, -\text{CH}_2\text{CMe}_2\text{CH}_2-, -\text{CMe}_2\text{CMe}_2-$ and $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CHMe}-$) have been prepared by the reaction of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with ammonium dithiophosphates, which on oxidation in dichloromethane solution yield complexes of the type $[\text{Co}\{\text{S}_2\text{PO}_2\text{G}\}_3]$.

The complexes of transition metals with sulfur donor ligands in general and 1,1'-dithio ligands (dithiophosphoric acids) in particular have been extensively studied¹. In continuation of our earlier work², we report here the complexes of *O,O'*-alkylenedithiophosphates with Co^{II} and Co^{III} .

Results and Discussion

Cobalt(II)bis(dithiophosphates) (Table 1) have been prepared by the reaction of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with ammonium dithiophosphates in oxygen-free ethanolic solution. Final extraction of the compounds has been carried out with the help of freshly boiled CH_2Cl_2 under inert atmosphere,

($\text{G} = -\text{CMe}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CHMe}-, -\text{CH}_2\text{CMe}_2\text{CH}_2-, -\text{CMe}_2\text{CMe}_2-$ and $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CHMe}-$)

Cobalt(III)tris(dithiophosphates) have been prepared by the above metathetical reactions with $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and excess of ammonium dithiophosphates in aqueous solutions by oxidation under refluxing condition. These reactions appear to be sluggish and require quite long time of refluxing for completion of the oxidation. The products are precipitated

out slowly as brown solids. Alternatively, these derivatives can also be prepared by oxidation of cobalt(II)bis(dithiophosphates) in dichloromethane solutions.

Cobalt(II)bis(dithiophosphates) are soluble in solvents like C_6H_6 , CHCl_3 and CH_2Cl_2 . On the other hand, only one cobalt(III)tris(dithiophosphate) is soluble ($\text{Co}\{\text{S}_2\text{PO}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_{12}\}_3$); all other cobalt(III) derivatives are practically insoluble in common organic solvents. Molecular weight data show monomeric nature for all the cobalt(II) and only soluble cobalt(III) derivative in chloroform solutions. Magnetic moments indicate diamagnetic character for the cobalt(III) derivatives, whereas the observed values (4.15–4.26 B.M.) are slightly lower than that reported for the high-spin tetrahedral cobalt(II) centres³.

In infrared spectra of these derivatives, the new band observed at $360\text{--}320\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicate the formation of Co–S bond⁴. The bands present at $1080\text{--}960$ and $960\text{--}845\text{ cm}^{-1}$ could be ascribed to $\nu(\text{P}=\text{O}-\text{C})$ and $[\text{P}-\text{O}-\text{C}]$ respectively. The bands at $990\text{--}910\text{ cm}^{-1}$ could be due to ring vibrations of cyclic dithiophosphate ligands⁵. The bands at $710\text{--}640\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are ascribed to $\nu_{\text{P}=\text{S}}$ vibrations indicating the bidentate chelation of dithiophosphato moiety with cobalt. The electronic spectra exhibit two major bands at $11978\text{--}11100$ and $16060\text{--}14900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which could be assigned respectively to ${}^4T_1(P) \leftarrow {}^4A_1$ and ${}^4T_1(F) \leftarrow {}^4A_2$ transitions. In the spectra of the only soluble cobalt(III) derivative $[\text{Co}\{\text{S}_2\text{PO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\}_3]$ the major bands observed at $14525, 24050$ and 19650 cm^{-1} may be assigned to transitions ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}(P), {}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ respectively^{6,7}. The ${}^1\text{H}$ nmr spectrum of $[\text{Co}\{\text{S}_2\text{PO}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_{12}\}_3]$ shows minor upfield shift (1.37 ppm) for the ($-\text{CH}_3$) signal in comparison to the free ligand spectrum, and ${}^{31}\text{P}$ nmr (at $\delta 118.20$) spectrum exhibits downfield shift of 15 ppm indicating the bidentate nature of the ligand⁵.

Thus based on the above facts tetrahedral and octahedral geometries have been tentatively proposed for cobalt in +2 and +3 oxidation states respectively⁶.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes

Compd.	M p °C	Analyses% Found/(Calcd.)	
		Co	S
$[\text{Co}\{\text{S}_2\text{PO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\}_2]$	168	12.30 (12.20)	26.60 (26.70)
$[\text{Co}\{\text{S}_2\text{PO}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_{10}\}_2]$	205	12.90 (13.00)	28.40 (28.30)
$[\text{Co}\{\text{S}_2\text{PO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\}_2]$	208	12.10 (12.20)	26.50 (26.70)
$[\text{Co}\{\text{S}_2\text{PO}_2\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\}_2]$	198	13.80 (13.90)	30.40 (30.20)
$[\text{Co}\{\text{S}_2\text{PO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\}_3]$	236	8.30 (8.50)	27.90 (27.80)
$[\text{Co}\{\text{S}_2\text{PO}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_{10}\}_3]$	240	9.00 (9.10)	29.50 (29.60)
$[\text{Co}\{\text{S}_2\text{PO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\}_3]$	238	8.55 (8.50)	27.70 (27.80)
$[\text{Co}\{\text{S}_2\text{PO}_2\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\}_3]$	210	9.60 (9.70)	31.90 (31.60)

Experimental

Ammonium salts of *O,O'*-alkylenedithiophosphoric acids were prepared as described earlier⁵. Ir spectra (KBr) and electronic spectra (dichloromethane) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 577 and Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometers respectively. ¹H nmr (CDCl₃) and ³¹P nmr (dichloromethane) spectra were recorded on a JEOL FX 90Q spectrometer for [Co{S₂PO₂C₆H₁₂}₃]. Molecular weights were measured on a Knauer vapour pressure osmometer in chloroform at 45°. Magnetic moment was measured on a Gouy balance at room temperature. Elemental analyses were carried out by standard methods⁸.

[Co{S₂PO₂C₅H₁₀}₂] : A freshly boiled ethanolic solution of CoCl₂.6H₂O (2.25 g) was mixed under constant stirring with the air-free aqueous solution of [NH₄{S₂PO₂C₅H₁₀}] (4.07 g) under inert atmosphere. Oxygen-free CH₂Cl₂ (20 ml) was added to the solution and stirred for 1 h. The green organic layer was separated, dried over anhydrous CaCl₂ and filtered. The volatiles from the filtrate were removed under reduced pressure to get green foamy solid (80%).

[Co{S₂PO₂C₅H₁₀}₃] : A mixture of aqueous solutions of CoCl₂.6H₂O (0.70 g) and [NH₄{S₂PO₂C₅H₁₀}] (1.98 g) was refluxed for 7 h with constant bubbling of oxygen. The colour of reaction mixture changed from pink to brown with brown coloured precipitate. The solid was washed with water and dried over P₂O₅ (yield 85%).

This derivative was alternatively prepared by bubbling oxygen through dichloromethane solution of [Co{S₂PO₂-

C₅H₁₀}₂] (1.78 g). The brown coloured solid that separated after 3 h of refluxing, was washed with CH₂Cl₂ and dried under reduced pressure (52% yield).

Acknowledgement

The authors are highly grateful to Prof. R. C. Mehrotra, Department of Chemistry, Rajasthan University, Jaipur, for academic discussions.

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